

Compromised taxonomy in the Eastern Himalaya: a critical appraisal of three recently described *Impatiens* (Balsaminaceae) species, with evidence of fabricated references, unverified AI-generated content, and failures of peer review and editorial oversight

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Abstract

The genus *Impatiens* L. (Balsaminaceae) has been the subject of discovery of new species from the Eastern Himalaya and Northeast India over the past decade (30 new taxa between 2016 and 2025). But in some cases, rapid publication of narrowly circumscribed taxa, combined with the increasing availability of generative artificial-intelligence (AI) writing tools, has created conditions in which descriptive and bibliographic errors can pass into the permanent taxonomic record. Here we provide a detailed, evidence based appraisal of three *Impatiens* species described in 2025–2026 by an overlapping author group: *I. chakhesangiana* M.Borah & S.Singh (Phytotaxa 742), *I. pfutserensis* S.Singh, B.Singh & M.Bhuyan (Taiwania 71), and *I. shamaii* S.Singh (Phytotaxa 728). Across the three papers we document a consistent set of problems: biologically impossible or internally contradictory measurements (e.g., a capsule simultaneously described as ‘linear’ and ‘fusiform’); diagnostic characters that contradict the accompanying figures and illustrations; failure to compare the new taxa with their most morphologically similar/allied and geographically proximate relatives; misleading distribution maps that share an identical, mis-scaled frame; inappropriate or self-serving citation; and reference lists containing non-existent papers, impossible volume numbers, and duplicated or internally inconsistent DOIs. The reference level errors in particular are characteristic of AI-assembled bibliographies generated without database verification and possible lack of review. One of the three taxa, *I. shamaii*, has already been formally synonymised under *I. leptocarpa* Hook.f. within weeks of publication. We argue that these are not isolated lapses but a recurrent pattern indicating inadequate manuscript preparation and a clear failure of editorial and peer review at the journals concerned. We recommend corrigenda or, where warranted, retraction, and propose concrete safeguards for the description of new taxa from biodiversity rich hotspot regions.

Keywords: Balsaminaceae, *Impatiens*, Eastern Himalaya, Northeast India, AI-generated content, research integrity, peer review, fabricated references, taxonomic rigour.

1. Introduction

Impatiens L. (Balsaminaceae) is one of the largest genera of flowering plants, with well over a thousand species distributed across the Old-World tropics and subtropics and major centres of diversity in tropical Africa, Madagascar, southern India and Sri Lanka, the Eastern Himalaya, and Southeast Asia (POWO 2026). The Eastern Himalaya and the adjoining states of Northeast India are an acknowledged centre of endemism for the genus, and the region has yielded a large number of new species in the recent years (e.g. Gogoi *et al.* 2018, Hareesh & Sabu 2020, Tiwari 2023, Gyeltshen *et al.* 2023 and Chowlu *et al.* 2025). This taxonomic productivity is welcome in principle: the floras of states such as Nagaland and Arunachal Pradesh remain incompletely documented, and genuine novelties undoubtedly await description.

Productivity, however, is not the same as rigour. The description of a new species is a nomenclatural act with permanent consequences: the protologue, the cited type, the diagnosis, and the comparative framework all enter the scientific record and constrain the work of every subsequent author. When descriptions are prepared hastily, when diagnostic characters are not checked against the specimens or against the figures, when the most similar relatives are not compared, and when reference lists are not verified, the result is not merely an imperfect paper but a durable source of confusion that consumes the time of later workers who must disentangle it.

Two developments have sharpened these concerns. First, the proliferation of journals and the speed of online publication have, in some cases, outpaced the capacity for expert review in specialised groups such as Balsaminaceae. Second, the rapid uptake of generative AI writing tools has introduced a new and recognisable class of error: fluent but vacuous prose, and confidently formatted but non-existent or internally inconsistent references that are qualitatively different from ordinary human carelessness.

In this paper we examine three *Impatiens* species described in late 2025 and 2026 by an overlapping group of authors, all centred on the same institution:

- *Impatiens chakhesangiana* M.Borah & S.Singh, from Phek district, Nagaland (Borah *et al.* 2026, Phytotaxa 742(2): 163–170);
- *Impatiens pfutserensis* S.Singh, B.Singh & M.Bhuyan, from Pfutsero, Phek district, Nagaland (Singh *et al.* 2026, Taiwaniana 71(2): 263–267); and
- *Impatiens shamaii* S.Singh, from Tawang district, Arunachal Pradesh (Singh 2025, Phytotaxa 728(1): 83–89), since synonymised under *I. leptocarpa* Hook.f. (Sherpa *et al.* 2025).

We treat each paper in turn, documenting the specific errors with reference to the published text, figures, and tables, and then draw the cases together in a synthesis that identifies the recurrent patterns. Our purpose is constructive: to correct the record, to flag the integrity, review and editorial failures that allowed these errors to be published, and to propose safeguards. We do not dispute that field collections were made, and we recognise that the underlying fieldwork in remote terrain is demanding and commendable. The criticism here is directed at manuscript preparation, the adequacy of the comparative and bibliographic work, and the review/editorial process and not at the existence of the collections.

2. Approach to the appraisal

Each published paper was examined in full, including all figures, illustrations, tables, type citations, and reference lists, using the final published PDF in each case. Morphological statements were checked for

internal consistency (text vs. diagnosis vs. abstract vs. table), against the accompanying photographs and line drawings, and against the standard morphology of *Impatiens*. Measurements were assessed for biological plausibility against the general ranges known for the genus and for the cited comparison taxa.

Reference lists were verified entry by entry against the primary literature and against the journal indices, JSTOR Global Plants, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), the International Plant Names Index (IPNI), and Plants of the World Online (POWO). DOIs were resolved and checked for internal consistency, in particular for the journals (such as *Phytotaxa*) whose DOI scheme encodes the volume number. Distribution maps were examined for the correspondence between the stated coordinate frame and the area actually depicted. Where a taxonomic conclusion has been independently reached in the subsequent literature; notably the synonymy of *I. shamaii*, that work is cited and accepted on its merits.

Indicators of AI-generated content were assessed conservatively. We treat fluent-but-empty prose, tautological closing sentences, and templated introduction structure as suggestive but not conclusive. We treat fabricated references, impossible volume numbers, and duplicated or internally inconsistent DOIs as very strong indicators, because these are the characteristic output of a language model assembling a bibliography from memory without access to a database, and are not readily explicable as ordinary transcription error. Throughout, we describe these features as patterns *consistent with* AI assistance rather than as proof of any particular tool or workflow.

3. Case 1: *Impatiens chakhesangiana* (*Phytotaxa* 742, 2026)

Borah *et al.* (2026) describe *I. chakhesangiana* from Porba village, Phek district, Nagaland, comparing it only with *I. drepanophora* Hook.f. The collection of a new to science *Impatiens* sp. from this underexplored region is credible, but the protologue contains internal contradictions, descriptive errors, a non-existent reference, and an inadequate comparative framework.

3.1 Morphological and descriptive errors

3.1.1 Flower length inconsistent with the given scale bar

The description gives the spur as “2–3 cm long” while the whole flower is stated to be “ca. 1.5–2 cm.” but notably flower length is inconsistent with the given scale bar in Fig 2E. At least one of the two measurements is wrong, and the comparative table does not resolve the contradiction because neither spur length nor total flower length is tabulated against the comparison taxon.

3.1.2 Leaf dimensions inconsistent with stated shape

The leaves are described as “1–1.38 cm × 5–10.3 cm in diameter”, but if scale bar in Fig. 2B is correct, leaf blade is approximately 15 cm long and 8 cm wide. Two problems then arise: First, leaf dimensions are conventionally length × width; as written, the leaf is 1–1.38 cm wide and 5–10.3 cm long, a 5–8:1 ratio that produces a linear to narrowly lanceolate blade yet the leaf is described as *ovate*, which is incompatible with that ratio. The dimensions appear transposed, or the values are erroneous. Second, “in diameter” is meaningless for a flat, bilaterally symmetrical laminar organ; ‘diameter’ applies to circular structures. The phrase should give length × width with no such qualifier.

3.1.3 ‘Caducous’ misapplied to the inflorescence

The text reads “*Inflorescence ... axillary, bracteate, caducous ...*” The term *caducous* (falling early) is properly applied to organs such as bracts, sepals, or stipules, not to an inflorescence as a whole. In context the authors most likely intended the bracts to be caducous. The misapplication reflects limited familiarity with standard morphological vocabulary or inadequate proofreading.

3.1.4 Flower colour ‘white’ contradicted by the petal descriptions and photographs

The flower is introduced as “*color white,*” but the subsequent detail describes the dorsal petal as “*pale pink to whitish with purplish tinges*” and the distal lobe as “*deep pink to violet.*” The flowers in Figs. 1 and 2 are clearly pale pink with violet elements, not white. The blanket statement ‘colour white’ contradicts both the rest of the description and the figures.

3.1.5 Sepal account internally inconsistent

The description states “*Sepals 3, petaloid, unequal, ca. 0.5–1.2 × 0.5 cm,*”. First of all, in all the species of *Impatiens* only lower sepal is petaloid and then, in the following sentences, authors give separate and different measurements for the two lateral sepals (ca. 1.5–2.5 mm) and the lower sepal (ca. 5–7 mm). The composite figure ‘0.5–1.2 × 0.5 cm’ matches neither the lateral nor the lower sepal dimensions subsequently provided, leaving the reader unable to reconcile the sepal data. A further omission concerns the same organ: in Fig. 2G (flower bud), a distinct beak is visible at the mouth of the lower sepal, yet this feature is not mentioned anywhere in the description.

3.2 Taxonomic and nomenclatural issues

3.2.1 Isotype without an individual accession number

The type is cited as “*Borah et al. 1080 (holotype CSIRNEIST!; isotype CSIRNEIST!).*” No distinct accession number is given for the isotype. Best practice under the *International Code of Nomenclature* (ICN) is to provide individual accession numbers so that holotype and isotype are unambiguously traceable; the repeated bare ‘CSIRNEIST!’ does not allow them to be distinguished in the herbarium register without further lookup.

3.2.2 Comparison restricted to a single, possibly incorrect, relative

The species is compared only with *I. drepanophora*, whereas *Impatiens deflexipetala* Biseshwori *et al.* (2019)- a morphologically very similar and geographically proximate taxon, described from neighbouring Manipur and likewise possessing pale pink flowers with an upcurved spur is entirely absent from the comparison. The principal apparent distinction (annual with runners in *I. deflexipetala* vs. perennial in *I. chakhesangiana*) is precisely the kind of character that demands an explicit differential diagnosis given the morphological and geographical proximity. Its omission leaves the novelty of the taxon insufficiently demonstrated.

3.3 Figures, illustrations, and the distribution map

- **Misspelled epithet in a figure caption.** The caption to Fig. 3 reads “*Impatiens chakhsangiana sp. nov.,*” dropping the ‘e’ from *chakhesangiana*. In a nomenclatural paper the correct spelling of the new name must be consistent throughout; the inconsistency is a proofreading failure that affects traceability.
- **Impossible scale bars.** Scale bars in Fig. 3A and 3C, and in Fig. 2A and 2D, are inconsistent with the structures depicted; a flower or floral part cannot correspond to a 16.3 cm bar. The bars appear mislabelled or misplaced and undermine the qualitative and quantitative value of the plates.

- **Inadequate floral dissection.** The plates lack a systematic floral dissection plate of the kind now standard in *Impatiens* taxonomy, in particular isolated lateral sepals against a contrasting (black) background, a section of the lower sepal/spur, and clearly labelled scale bars for individual parts in the field photographs. The line drawing partially compensates but does not substitute for photographic dissection.
- **Misleading map frame.** The distribution map presents coordinate frames for a small local area while simultaneously displaying a whole India inset, in a manner that misrepresents the spatial scale of the known occurrence. The same map frame design recurs in the other two papers (see Discussion).

3.4 Reference errors

3.4.1 A non-existent reference: ‘Gogoi (2019)’

The paper cites “Gogoi, R. (2019) *Contribution to the taxonomy of Impatiens in Northeast India. Rheedeia 29(1): 1–12.*” This article does not exist: the opening paper of *Rheedeia 29(1)* is a revision of *Ceropegia* in India (Kambale & Yadav 2019), not a contribution to *Impatiens*. The reference cannot be located in JSTOR, Google Scholar, ResearchGate, or the journal’s own index for that issue. The same non-existent reference also appears in Singh (2025) (Case 3), which strongly suggests an AI-generated entry propagated between papers from the same group without verification. No specialist familiar with *Rheedeia* or with R. Gogoi’s publication record would have accepted it, and its survival clearly demonstrates that neither the authors nor the handling editor checked the reference list.

3.4.2 Other bibliographic problems

- **Erroneous ‘Flowering plants of India’ citation.** ‘Gogoi, R., Upadhyay, A.K. & Rathakrishnan, N.C. (2020) Flowering plants of India. Botanical Survey of India, Kolkata, 706 pp.’ is incorrect. The correct reference is the Balsaminaceae chapter: Gogoi, Upadhyay & Rathakrishnan (2020), Balsaminaceae, in Mao & Dash (eds), *Flowering Plants of India: An Annotated Checklist (Dicotyledons)*, Vol. 1, pp. 204–223.
- **Citation/alphabetisation mismatch.** The *I. nagorum* paper is cited in text as ‘Moaakum *et al.*, 2017’ but listed under ‘Moa’ in the references; the in-text form should be ‘Moa *et al.*, 2017’ to match the entry under which it is alphabetised. (The reference is also misattributed to ‘A.A. Mao’ as first author in the companion *Taiwania* paper - please see Case 2.)
- **Page range error.** The pagination given for Huang *et al.* (2003) *i.e.* 61-268 is incorrect. Correct pagination is 261-280.
- **Outdated or inappropriate sourcing.** Toppin (1920) is cited where the more recent and relevant Ruchisansakun *et al.* (2018) would be expected; a recent reinstatement (Mondal, Sherpa & Gogoi 2025, *Nelumbo*) and the typification of *I. parkinsonii* (Gogoi, Odyuo & Daimary 2015, *Telopea*) are not cited despite their direct relevance. The species count of ‘1167’ is attributed to Mabberley (2008), Bhaskar (2012), and Yu (2012), none of which gives that figure; a current POWO citation (already consulted by the authors) would be the appropriate source.
- **Confusion of similar epithets.** *I. cuspidata* (a Western Ghats species) is conflated with *I. cuspidifera* (Eastern Himalayan species), recently reinstated by Mondal *et al.* (2025); and the state checklist that

should be cited for the number of *Impatiens* in Nagaland (Mao, Odyuo, Verma & Singh 2017, Check List of Flora of Nagaland) is not used.

3.5 Other editorial issues

- **Microscope misdescribed.** The ‘phase contrast microscope (INFINITY iOX-700 Nx)’ is a digital trinocular microscope, not a phase-contrast instrument; phase contrast requires specific objectives and a condenser annulus and is not used for routine dissection of *Impatiens*. The equipment is either misdescribed or the technique misidentified.
- **Provenance of the 2024 material unclear.** Collections are reported from August 2024 and September 2025, with the holotype dated 09 Sept. 2025, but the Materials and Methods do not state whether 2024 duplicates were prepared or deposited, or whether the two seasons sampled the same population.

4. Case 2: *Impatiens pfutserensis* (Taiwania 71, 2026)

Singh *et al.* (2026) describe *I. pfutserensis* from Pfutsero, Phek district, Nagaland, comparing it only with morphologically less related *I. stenantha* Hook.f. and *I. prainii* Hook.f. In addition to morphological and bibliographic errors, this paper shows the clearest stylistic indicators of AI-assisted drafting among the three.

4.1 Indicators consistent with AI-generated content

4.1.1 Discussion: fluent but vacuous

- “*These narrowly endemic species may represent recent evolutionary radiations or ancient relictual lineages shaped by quaternary climatic shifts.*” This advances two mutually exclusive hypotheses (recent radiation vs. ancient relict) with no evidence, citation, or argument - the hedged, ‘both-options-covered’ phrasing characteristic of AI text asked to sound scientific without data.
- “*Such subtle but consistent traits are typical in Impatiens, where microhabitat specialisation drives rapid speciation.*” An unreferenced causal claim stated as established fact.
- “*Conservation efforts are required for the conservation of threatened species.*” A tautology containing no information: a recognisable AI ‘closing sentence’ pattern.

4.1.2 Introduction: templated filler

The Introduction follows the canonical global → continental → regional → local template and is padded with non-specific phrasing such as “*collectively reflecting the genus’s evolutionary history, ecological adaptability, and diversification across varied tropical and subtropical habitats,*” which states the obvious and cites nothing new.

4.1.3 Etymology: travel-brochure language

The etymology states that Pfutsero is “*scenic*” and that “*This region is known for its scenic beauty and rich biodiversity,*” using ‘scenic’ twice in consecutive sentences is promotional language not used in scientific etymology sections.

4.2 Critical scientific and morphological errors

- **Anther 0.2 mm across.** Anthers in *Impatiens* are typically 1–3 mm; an anther ‘ca. 0.2 mm across’ would be near microscopic. This is almost certainly a typographic error (probably for 2 mm) but was published as stated.
- **Dorsal petal ‘orbicular’ but twice as long as wide.** The dorsal petal is called ‘orbicular’ yet measured 1.9–2.3 × 0.8–1.2 cm i.e. nearly 2:1 which is obovate or narrowly ovate, not orbicular.
- **Capsule ‘ridged’ in text vs. smooth in the photograph.** The description and Table 1 state a ridged capsule, but Fig. 1F appears to show a smooth, unridged surface.
- **Spur length inconsistent across three sections.** The stated upper limit of the spur differs between sections, so the correct value cannot be determined from the paper.
- **Inflorescence: ‘8-flowered’ contradicted by the figures.** An exactly 8-flowered inflorescence is cited as diagnostic in the Abstract, Diagnosis, and Table 1, but the Description hedges to “*typically 8 flowered,*” and the habit photograph and illustration (Fig. 1A; Fig. 2) show only two to three flowers. A fixed count used as a key character, contradicted both by ‘typically’ and by the authors’ own images, cannot stand and is the kind of conspicuous inconsistency that competent review should have caught.
- **Figure scale bars (Fig. 1D, 1E).** Fig. 1D labels the inflorescence ‘4.5 cm’ although the peduncle is stated to be 1–2 cm; in a plant only 15–30 cm tall the total inflorescence is unlikely to reach 4.5 cm. If the 4 cm bar in Fig. 1E were correct, the flower would be almost 10 cm long. The bars appear mislabelled.
- **Conservation status reasoning.** The paper says the restricted range ‘might suggest Endangered (EN)’ but then assigns Data Deficient (DD) merely because only one locality has been searched. DD is for cases of genuinely insufficient information to assess extinction risk, not a default for limited survey effort.

4.3 Taxonomic and nomenclatural errors

- **‘Distinguished with the later.’** The Diagnosis reads ‘can be distinguished with the later’: one distinguishes a species *from* another, not ‘with’; and ‘later’ should be ‘latter’. An elementary error in the most formally significant section of the paper.
- **Comparison taxa possibly incorrect.** Beyond *I. stenantha* and *I. prainii*, purple flowered forms of *I. drepanophora*, *I. siculifera* var. *porphyria*, *I. tirbinensis*, *I. deflexipetala*, *I. chakhesangiana* (all documented with purple-flowered forms and later described from the same district and from the same species complex) are not considered, leaving the comparative framework incomplete.

4.4 Writing and reference errors

- **Grammar.** ‘one of the most species-rich genus in Angiosperms’ (should be ‘genera’; ‘angiosperms’ lower-case); ‘the later’ for ‘the latter’; and a comparison clause mis-structured so that ‘branched, solid’ reads as a comparison to ‘adventitious roots’ rather than to stem type.
- **‘Sanctuart’.** Ramasubbu *et al.* (2020) is cited with ‘Kodaikkanal Wildlife Sanctuart’ for ‘Sanctuary’.
- **Duplicated reference.** Hooker (1874) and Hooker (1875) are functionally the same work (Flora of British India, Vol. 1); the 1875 entry adds nothing. Anyone familiar with the Flora of British India would recognise the redundancy.

- **Inappropriate source.** Rheede (1689), a 17th-century horticultural compendium, is cited for petal fusion in a 2026 taxonomic paper; Hooker (1874) alone would suffice.
- **Mis-attributed first author: a clear AI indicator.** The *I. nagorum* paper is listed as ‘Mao, A.A., Dey, S., Adamowski, W., Gogoi, R. 2017’. The first author is Moaakum Moa, not A.A. Mao. The correct citation is ‘Moa, M., Dey, S., Adamowski, W. & Gogoi, R. (2017) *Impatiens nagorum* sp. nov. (Balsaminaceae)... Phytotaxa 308(2): 275–282.’ Had the authors opened the cited paper even once, this would have been obvious.
- **Non-existent reference.** ‘Singh, P. 2016. Endemic species of *Impatiens* in Northeast India. *Rheedea* 26(1): 1–10’ does not exist; no such paper appears in *Rheedea* 26(1). This is a strong AI-fabrication indicator that was not checked by authors, reviewers and editor.
- **Ambiguous morphology.** ‘petiole ... tip light pink, subglobose, stalked’ - ‘subglobose, stalked’ describes a gland, not a petiole tip, yet stipular glands are stated to be absent; the structure is left unexplained. A ‘Horn’ is labelled in Fig. 1 without definition in the text.

4.5 Source quality and self-citation problems

- **Misquoted figure.** ‘more than 1,000 species native to Asia’ is attributed to Song *et al.* (2021), which states only that there are more than 1,000 balsams worldwide.
- **Brazen self-citation.** Singh *et al.* 2021a,b are cited in support of the ‘unexplored’ status of the Eastern Himalaya, but both concern the Western Himalaya (a flora of a Kashmir valley and a new fern from Kashmir) absolutely irrelevant to the stated point.
- **Wrong kind of source for diversity figures.** Species counts and statements about balsam richness in Northeast India and the Western Ghats are sourced to individual new-species papers rather than to floras or monographs.
- **Closely similar species by the same authors omitted.** The companion paper Borah *et al.* (2026) describing *I. chakhesangiana* (Case 1), from the same district, is not cited or compared, despite obvious relevance.

5. Case 3: *Impatiens shamaii* (Phytotaxa 728, 2025)

Taxonomic status note. *Impatiens shamaii* S.Singh (2025) has been synonymised under *Impatiens leptocarpa* Hook.f. by Sherpa, Lepcha, Mondal & Gogoi (2025, *Nelumbo* 67(2): 35–40). That synonymy is well supported and is accepted here. The *Nelumbo* paper resolves the taxonomic question but does not address the research-integrity indicators (fabricated references, AI-consistent content) or the peer-review failure documented below; the two issues are independent and both require acknowledgement.

Singh (2025) describes *I. shamaii* from Tawang district, Arunachal Pradesh, at 3988 m, comparing it only with *I. albopetala* Gogoi & Borah (2016). The manuscript is compromised by dense morphological contradictions, reference fabrication, and most consequentially failure to compare with the true closest relative, *I. leptocarpa*, which was already documented in the literature and under which the species has since been synonymised.

5.1 Indicators consistent with AI-generated content

5.1.1 Reference list: non-existent papers and inconsistent DOIs

Fabricated or internally inconsistent references are the most diagnostic indicators. Independent expert examination (Adamowski, Balsaminaceae Brief, November 2025) reported at least three non-existent papers in the reference list. The following are documented from the published list:

Reference	Problem	Interpretation
<i>Gogoi & Borah (2015c)</i>	Carries the same DOI (10.1080/00837792.2016.1253913) as Gogoi & Borah (2016), a different paper	DOI duplication; one entry cannot exist as cited
<i>Hareesh et al. (2017)</i>	DOI string contains ‘317’ but the stated reference is Phytotaxa 308(3): 289–294	Impossible DOI (Phytotaxa encodes volume in DOI)
<i>Myers et al. (2000)</i>	Cited as ‘Nature 40: 853–858’; correct is Nature 403: 853–858	Confabulated volume number
‘ <i>Tiwai, U.L.</i> ’ (2023)	Author surname mis-spelled vs. in-text ‘Tiwari’; unverifiable as cited	Reference not retrievable as written
<i>Singh, N.P. (2001)</i>	Cited as source for Indian species count; reported non-existent as cited	Unverifiable
<i>Gogoi & Borah (2013)</i>	‘Phytotaxa 86(2)’ reported non-existent as cited	Unverifiable
<i>Gogoi (2019)</i>	Rheede 29(1): 1–12 — does not exist (same fabricated entry as Case 1)	Cross-propagated fabrication

Each of these is a structurally plausible citation that fails on verification the signature of a bibliography assembled from a language model’s memory rather than from a database. A DOI is unique to a single publication; two different papers sharing one, and a Phytotaxa DOI whose embedded volume contradicts the stated volume, cannot arise from ordinary human transcription error.

5.1.2 Acknowledgements: three grammatical persons in three sentences

Three consecutive sentences shift person: “*The author would like to express his gratitude...*” (third-person singular), “*I would like to sincerely thank...*” (first-person singular), “*We are also thankful...*” (first-person plural). This inconsistency is a recognisable artefact of text assembled from differently framed prompts and is not how a single author writes an acknowledgement.

5.1.3 Non-existent botanical terms: ‘pillate’ and ‘plinear’

The Description uses two terms that do not exist in botanical usage: “*pillate with green tip*” (for the petiole; intended ‘pilose’ or ‘piliferous’) and “*plinear or setaceous*” (for the stipules; intended ‘linear’). Both are near-phonetic or character-insertion substitutions consistent with AI text generation or heavily AI-assisted drafting that received no expert human proofing; both survived reviews and editorial work.

5.2 Critical morphological errors

5.2.1 Capsule shape, the key diagnostic character is self-contradictory

The capsule, used to distinguish the new species, is described differently in every formal section:

Location	Capsule description
Abstract	“fusiform capsule” — given as a key distinguishing character

Location	Capsule description
Diagnosis	“capsule smooth fusiform (vs. slightly ribbed linear)”
Description	“Capsule linear, 4–5 × 0.1 cm long ... smooth” — contradicts the above
Table 1	“fusiform, smooth, black turning after mature”

‘Linear’ and ‘fusiform’ are mutually exclusive. The contradiction recurs four times without correction. A capsule ‘4–5 × 0.1 cm’ *i.e.* 40–50:1 is itself an extraordinary and doubtful proportion. As capsule shape is a primary diagnostic character, this directly weakens the species concept as published.

5.2.2 Spur and red-dot characters: Diagnosis vs. Description

- **Spur.** The Diagnosis describes spur as ‘*sharply downward-curved with swollen apex*’; while in the Description author describe the spur as ‘*tip erect, straight or sometimes slightly downwards*’; Table 1 agrees with the Description and contradicts the Diagnosis. Since the Diagnosis is the comparative statement of record under the ICN, its contradiction by the Description is both a scientific and a nomenclatural problem. In the published figures the spur in fact appears almost straight, consistent with the Description and Table 1 rather than with the ‘*sharply downward-curved*’ claim given in the Diagnosis.
- **Red dots.** The Diagnosis places red dots on the dorsal petal; the Description places them only on the lateral petals (not on the dorsal petal) which is a factual contradiction between the two most important sections.

5.2.3 Other morphological problems

- **Lateral sepal number.** The paper states two lateral sepals for the new species and claims four for *I. albopetala*, contradicting the original description; the comparison appears to confuse sepal pairs with individual sepals. In *I. leptocarpa*, Sherpa *et al.* (2025) describe four lateral sepals in two pairs.
- **Altitude.** The habitat is given as 3800–4500 m; the type was collected at 3988 m. An upper limit of 4500 m would be a record among balsams worldwide (Adamowski 2025) and requires corroboration - multiple high elevation localities, herbarium specimens, photographs, associated flora but none of which is provided.

5.3 The central taxonomic failure: the closest relative was not compared

The species was compared only with *I. albopetala*. The correct comparison taxon is *I. leptocarpa* Hook.f., known from the same elevational zone across the Eastern Himalaya (West Bengal, Sikkim, Nepal, Bhutan, China). That taxon was already documented in readily findable literature - Tian *et al.* (2024, Phytotaxa 661(1): 47–62), published in the same journal one year earlier and explicitly providing supplementary knowledge on *I. leptocarpa*, and Gogoi *et al.* (2021), which illustrates it in colour with full description. Neither is cited.

Sherpa *et al.* (2025) subsequently demonstrated that the characters used to separate *I. shamaii* from *I. albopetala* *i.e.* flower count, red dot distribution, spur shape, dorsal petal morphology - all fall within the variation of *I. leptocarpa*, and formally synonymised the name, noting that the differentiation relied on ‘superfluous and insufficient characters’ and compared the new species with a ‘distinctly different taxon.’ The synonymy was independently identified within weeks of publication and formalised about six weeks later, a measure of how conspicuous the error was, and of the omission of the relevant comparison from both the manuscript and the review.

5.4 Type citation, species count, figures, and writing

- **Both type sheets at one herbarium.** Holotype and the sole isotype are both at NEIST; ICN Recommendation 7A.2. advises distributing isotypes to different herbaria for redundancy and accessibility.
- **Outdated species count contradicting a cited source.** ‘nearly 210 species’ for India derives from Singh (2001), while POWO (2025) cited in the same sentence and recent checklists record ~279–300. Had POWO & recent publications actually been consulted, the current figure was available.
- **Inadequate illustration.** No formal floral dissection is provided; dissected parts in Fig. 3 are dried, discoloured, and minimally scaled. Capsule shape (the central contradiction) cannot be confirmed from Fig. 2G.
- **Writing.** ‘theis species are distinct’ (for ‘these’); ‘angiospermic genera comprises of 1167 species’ (‘comprises of’ is non-standard and AI typical); ‘shinning’ for ‘shining’; ‘Acknowledgement’ for ‘Acknowledgements’; and a Diagnosis whose parallel (‘vs. ...’) structure breaks down midway. The Materials and Methods are repetitive and partly incoherent (‘documenting the plant’s morphological, habitat notes and based on studies of morphological characters’), and present specimen handling in an illogical order (compared, then preserved, then compared).

6. Discussion: recurrent patterns across the three papers

Examined individually, each paper could be dismissed as an unusually error prone publication. Examined together — three papers, one overlapping author group, two journals, and the same handling editor for the two Phytotaxa papers, they reveal a consistent pattern that points to systemic problems in preparation and review rather than isolated slips.

6.1 Fabricated and inconsistent references: a shared AI fingerprint

All three papers contain references that fail verification, and the failures are of a specific kind: non-existent papers (‘Gogoi 2019’ in both Cases 1 and 3; ‘Singh, P. 2016’ in Case 2; ‘Singh, N.P. 2001’ and ‘Gogoi & Borah 2013’ in Case 3), mis-attributed first authorship (‘A.A. Mao’ for Moaakum Moa in Case 2), impossible volume-encoded DOIs and duplicated DOIs (Case 3), and confabulated volume numbers (‘Nature 40’ in Case 3). The reappearance of the identical fabricated ‘Gogoi (2019), Rheedea 29(1): 1–12’ in two separate papers is particularly telling: a fabricated entry has propagated between manuscripts from the same group without ever being checked. These are not the errors of a hurried but competent author transcribing real references; they are the characteristic output of a generative language model producing plausible citations from memory. We therefore regard AI assistance in assembling these manuscripts at least their bibliographies, and in Cases 2 and 3 portions of the prose, as strongly indicated.

6.2 Biologically impossible and internally contradictory data

Each paper contains at least one datum that is impossible or self-contradictory: a leaf whose dimensions contradict its stated shape (Case 1); an anther 0.2 mm across, a stated flower count contradicted by the figures, and a spur length that differs between sections (Case 2); and a capsule described as both ‘linear’ and ‘fusiform’ four times over, at 40–50:1 proportions (Case 3). Diagnostic characters routinely conflict with the accompanying photographs and illustrations. That such errors appear in the diagnoses and

descriptions, the most consequential and most scrutinised parts of a new species paper, indicates that the morphological data were never checked against the specimens, the figures, or a Balsaminaceae reference.

6.3 Inadequate comparison with the most similar taxa

In every case the new species is compared with a small, sometimes incorrect, set of relatives while the most morphologically similar/allied and geographically proximate taxon is omitted: *I. deflexipetala* for *I. chakhesangiana*; purple-flowered forms of *I. drepanophora*, *I. chakhesangiana* and *I. siculifera* var. *porphyria* for *I. pfutserensis*; and, most seriously, *I. leptocarpa* for *I. shamaii*, an omission that directly caused a synonymy. Notably, the two Nagaland papers describe similar plants from the same district yet do not cite or compare with one another. A rigorous differential diagnosis against the nearest relatives is the minimum evidentiary standard for erecting a new species; it is absent here.

6.4 Misleading distribution maps: an identical, geometrically incoherent frame

On a locality map, the coordinate graticule (the latitude and longitude ticks that frame the figure) is a precise statement of geographic extent and projection. It can be correct for only one map, at one scale, at a time. In all three papers, however, the graticule is wrapped around a multi panel composite whose panels depict areas differing by two to three orders of magnitude: a continental, whole India locator placed beside a state or district level map. Because both panels are enclosed by the same set of coordinate ticks, the frame is geometrically valid for at most one of them and grossly wrong for the others. This is not a stylistic quibble; it is an elementary GIS error that renders the coordinate information meaningless.

The consequences are striking when stated plainly. In *I. shamaii*, the all India inset is enclosed within a frame ticked 91°–92°E and 27°–28°N, implying that the whole of India spans a single degree of longitude when it in fact extends across roughly thirty. In *I. pfutserensis*, the reverse: a state level elevation map of Nagaland is enclosed within a frame ticked 70°–120°E, implying the state spans fifty degrees of longitude rather than its actual ~2. In *I. chakhesangiana*, the whole country and whole state insets sit within a district scale frame (94°10'–94°50'E), implying India occupies forty minutes of arc.

Each composite confirms its own incoherence internally: it carries two or more scale bars at mutually incompatible scales beneath a single graticule, a '2,000 km' bar beside a '120 km' bar in *I. pfutserensis*, and an '1,820 km' bar beside a '50 km' bar in *I. shamaii*. Two scale bars differing by more than an order of magnitude cannot both be true under one coordinate frame; their coexistence is direct evidence that the frame does not, and cannot, apply to both panels. The insets carry no graticule of their own to resolve the ambiguity, and in *I. chakhesangiana* several of the latitude labels are rotated and partly garbled, compounding the problem.

A further, separate error appears in the *I. pfutserensis* map: the sampling point is labelled 'Sampling Point (Kikruma, Nagaland)', whereas the type citation, the etymology, the abstract, and the title all give the type locality as Pfutsero. Kikruma and Pfutsero are distinct villages; a locality map that names a different village from the one designated in the protologue is an internal contradiction between figure and text on the single most important datum a distribution map exists to convey where the type was collected.

Finally, the three maps are clearly products of a single template: the same software defaults, the same North arrow and legend box styling, the same composite layout, and decisively the same conceptual error reproduced three times. A coordinate frame that places the whole of India within one degree of longitude is the kind of mistake that is obvious at a glance to anyone who has ever prepared a locality map, and that any competent reviewer or thematic editor should have caught immediately. That it survived in three separate papers across two different journals indicates that the figures were neither prepared nor refereed with even minimal cartographic care, and reinforces the broader impression of a shared, lightly checked production pipeline. A correct presentation is straightforward: give each panel its own graticule and scale bar, or use a single consistent projection with one correct graticule and an uncoordinated locator inset standard practice that the authors did not follow in any of the three papers.

6.5 Inappropriate sourcing and self-citation

Diversity figures and statements about regional richness are repeatedly sourced to individual new species papers rather than to floras, checklists, or monographs; current totals are taken from outdated works even where the authors cite POWO in the same breath; a worldwide figure is misreported as an Asian one; and irrelevant self-citations (Western Himalayan studies cited for an Eastern Himalayan point) inflate the reference list. These practices weaken the factual foundation of the introductions and suggest citation by association rather than by verification.

6.6 Editorial and peer-review failure

The errors documented here are not subtle: a four-fold capsule contradiction, an inflorescence count contradicted by the paper's own photographs, fabricated references, and DOIs whose embedded volume numbers are internally impossible would all be caught by any attentive reviewer or editor with relevant expertise, and several by just routine database checks. The synonymy of *I. shamaii* was identified by experts within weeks of publication, drawing on a paper (Tian *et al.* 2024) published in the same journal. The most parsimonious explanation for the survival of these errors is that the manuscripts received inadequate expert scrutiny and perhaps in some instances, plausibly, little or no effective peer review. The two Phytotaxa papers share the same handling editor; the editorial responsibility for that oversight is correspondingly concentrated.

6.7 Breach of the publishing journal's own AI-use policy

Two of the three papers *viz.* *I. chakhesangiana* (Phytotaxa 742) and *I. shamaii* (Phytotaxa 728) were published in Phytotaxa, whose author guidelines carry an explicit policy on AI tools. That policy states that AI tools “*should not be used to generate data, figures, ideas, or conclusions*” within manuscripts; it permits them only to improve readability and to adjust the size, contrast, or brightness of images; it requires that, where AI tools are used, the authors disclose in the manuscript which specific tool was used and how; and it places ultimate responsibility for the accuracy, originality, and ethics of the manuscript including any AI-assisted parts on the authors.

Measured against that policy, the two Phytotaxa papers are problematic on two independent counts. First, the reference level failures documented above, non-existent papers, an impossible volume encoded DOI, a DOI duplicated between two different papers, a confabulated journal volume, and the identical fabricated ‘Gogoi (2019)’ entry shared between these two papers are most parsimoniously explained by AI-generated reference content, which is precisely the kind of generative use the policy prohibits. Second, neither paper carries any statement disclosing AI assistance; if AI tools were used in their preparation, as the cumulative evidence indicates, the absence of disclosure is itself a breach of the policy's mandatory disclosure requirement. The two horns of this dilemma are not mutually exclusive: the material may have been generated in a manner the policy forbids, or AI-assisted and undisclosed, or both. Because the policy assigns ultimate responsibility for accuracy and originality to the authors, a defence resting on ‘tool error’ is expressly foreclosed.

Two qualifications should be stated plainly. The wording cited is the current Phytotaxa author guideline; the authors and the journal should confirm its precise effective date relative to each submission, although AI-disclosure requirements of this kind were already standard across the major taxonomic publishers well before these papers were submitted. By contrast, the third paper *i.e.* *I. pfutserensis* appeared in Taiwania,

whose current author guidelines contain no statement on AI tools at all. The same conduct in that paper therefore cannot be tested against a journal specific rule; it nonetheless contravenes the widely adopted, COPE aligned norms that require disclosure of AI assistance and hold authors accountable for AI-assisted content. The contrast is itself instructive: where an explicit policy existed (Phytotaxa) it was not enforced at review, and where none existed (Taiwania) the same problems passed unflagged which is why both, a clear policy and its active enforcement are needed, not one without the other.

6.8 On the underlying biology

Our critique concerns the published work, not the prior probability that genuine novelties exist in these regions. *I. chakhesangiana* and *I. pfutserensis* may yet prove distinct, but neither is adequately demonstrated as published: the photographs lack the floral dissections needed to confirm novelty, and the most morphologically similar/allied taxa are not compared. Resolving their status will require recollection at the type localities and proper comparative study. *I. shamaii*, by contrast, is now settled as a synonym of *I. leptocarpa*.

Recommended actions

We recommend the following, addressed to the authors, the journals, and the wider community describing Balsaminaceae from the Eastern Himalaya:

- **Corrigenda or retraction.** For *I. chakhesangiana* and *I. pfutserensis*, the journals should require corrigenda addressing, at minimum, the impossible and contradictory measurements, the figure/scale-bar errors, the misleading maps, the missing comparisons, and the fabricated or erroneous references. For *I. shamaii*, a formal Notice of Concern or corrigendum should acknowledge both the synonymy under *I. leptocarpa* and the reference fabrications; retraction should be considered given the combination of a fundamental taxonomic error with research integrity failures.
- **Human-expert correction only.** Any corrections must be prepared by human experts with Balsaminaceae knowledge and must not be drafted with AI tools.
- **Reference integrity checks at review.** Editors should institute basic reference verification (DOI resolution, volume/DOI consistency, existence checks against journal indices) for new species submissions, which would have caught most of the bibliographic errors documented here.
- **Mandatory comparison with the nearest relatives and current checklists.** Protologues should be required to compare the new taxon explicitly with its most similar and most geographically proximate relatives, and to reconcile species counts and distributional claims against current floras, regional monographs, and POWO at the date of submission.
- **Adequate illustration.** A complete, scaled floral dissection (lateral sepals, lower sepal/spur in section, dorsal petal, lateral petal pairs, androecium, pistil, capsule) should be a condition of acceptance for species argued to be novel on floral characters.
- **Disclosure of AI use.** Journals should adopt and enforce clear policies on the disclosure of generative AI assistance, with post submission screening of reference lists for the fabrication patterns described here.

Conclusion

Three *Impatiens* papers published in 2025–2026 by an overlapping author group share a consistent and serious set of defects: biologically impossible or internally contradictory morphological data, diagnostic characters contradicted by their own figures, omission of the most relevant morphologically allied taxa, misleading distribution maps built on a shared template, inappropriate and self-serving citation, and reference lists containing non-existent papers and impossible or duplicated DOIs that are most readily (only) explained by unverified AI-assisted drafting and a failure of authorial verification. One of the three names has already fallen into synonymy within weeks of publication. Crucially, these are not failures of authorship alone. That contradictions visible in the papers' own figures, references that fail a basic existence check, and maps that misplace whole regions by orders of magnitude were all passed for publication points to a corresponding failure of peer review and editorial oversight: the reviewers and handling editors did not apply the elementary checks that would have caught these errors before they entered the permanent record. Individually regrettable, together these cases indicate a breakdown of the basic safeguards, careful preparation, comparison with the literature, reference verification, and competent expert review on which the integrity of the taxonomic record depends. Correcting these specific papers is necessary but not sufficient; the recurrence of the same failures across journals argues for the systematic safeguards proposed above. The botanically rich and still under-documented Eastern Himalaya deserves new species descriptions that will stand (based on scientific evidence and research ethics), not ones that the next worker must spend years undoing.

Acknowledgements

The authors (AS & PNL) thank Dr. Prasanna N. S. (Postdoctoral Research Associate and Project Manager, ATREE) for suggestions that helped in drafting the manuscript, and Dr. Darshan Shankar (Vice Chancellor, TDU Bengaluru) for logistical support and encouragement. WA acknowledges logistic support from the International Centre for Research on Forest Ecosystems, Białowieża, Poland.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests. This appraisal is offered as post-publication scientific commentary in the interest of the integrity of the taxonomic science record.

Data availability

All material discussed is contained in the three published papers cited and in the publicly available literature, herbarium records, and databases (POWO, GBIF, IPNI, JSTOR Global Plants) referenced herein.

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